

1 S1 text

2 Method A

3 The estimation of a state variable f across the root tissues, for example Cauchy stress or
4 velocity, is approximated by the following integral at a location $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z) \in \mathbb{R}^3$

$$\langle f(\mathbf{x}) \rangle_h = \int_{\Omega} f(\mathbf{x}') W(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, h) d\mathbf{x}', \quad (1)$$

5 where the kernel W is a positive, monotone decreasing function of the interaction distance
6 between two particles $|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|$, and the smoothing length h controls the size of the interaction
7 region. The kernel W satisfies for $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^3$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{|h| \rightarrow 0} W(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, h) &= \delta(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'), \\ \int_{\Omega} W(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, h) d\mathbf{x}' &= 1, \\ \int_{\Omega} \nabla W(|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|, h) d\mathbf{x}' &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

8 The SPH method computes (1) by a summation over a set of discrete data points corre-
9 sponding to particles. Thus, the approximation f_i of the function f at the particle i located
10 at \mathbf{x}_i results from the following sum over all the particles j in the neighborhood

$$\begin{aligned} \langle f_i \rangle_h &\approx \sum_j f_j \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} W(r_{ij}, h), \\ \langle \nabla f_i \rangle_h &\approx \sum_j f_j \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} \nabla W(r_{ij}, h), \end{aligned}$$

11 where $r_{ij} = |\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j|$, m_j is the mass and ρ_j is the density of the particle j .

12 In roots, the distribution of cells and their size vary greatly with time, and the classical SPH
13 precision suffers from heterogeneous distributions. To mitigate these effects, we implement
14 the SPH with anisotropic kernels and gradient correction. To account for anisotropic volume
15 changes, the smoothing length used to compute the contribution of a particle j on a particle
16 i is denoted h_{ij} and defined as the radius of the smoothing ellipsoid \mathbf{H} in the direction
17 r_{ij} . \mathbf{H} dimensions are proportional to the cell ellipsoid with a factor \bar{H} . We refer to the
18 review of Liu and Liu [2], for the derivation of the anisotropic kernel. The corrected gradient
19 formulation introduced by Zhang and Liu [3] follows

$$\tilde{\nabla}W(r_{ij}, h_{ij}) = \nabla W(r_{ij}, h_{ij}) \odot \left[\sum_k \frac{m_k}{\rho_k} (\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}_i) \odot \nabla W(r_{ik}, h_{ik}) \right]^{-1},$$

20 where i and j label two different particles, k labels the particles in the neighborhood of i ,
21 and \odot denotes the component-wise product. Here, h_{ij} is the radius of the ellipsoid \mathbf{H} .

22 The velocity gradient of particles is expressed as

$$\langle \nabla u_i \rangle = \sum_j \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} (u_j - u_i) \tilde{\nabla}W(r_{ij}, h_{ij}).$$

23 The variation of mass and momentum is approximated by

$$\left\langle \frac{D\rho_i}{Dt} \right\rangle = \sum_j m_j (u_j - u_i) \cdot \tilde{\nabla}W(r_{ij}, h_{ij}) + \gamma_i, \quad (2)$$

$$\left\langle \frac{Du_i}{Dt} \right\rangle = \sum_j m_j \left(\frac{\sigma_i + \sigma_j}{\rho_i \rho_j} + \Pi_{\alpha, ij} \mathbb{I} \right) \cdot \tilde{\nabla}W(r_{ij}, h_{ij}), \quad (3)$$

24 with $\sigma_i = (P(\rho_i) + p_i) \mathbb{I} + \tau_i \in \mathcal{M}_{3 \times 3}(\mathbb{R})$. The artificial viscosity term $\Pi_{\alpha, ij}$ with $\alpha \in [0, 1]$
25 is described in [2] and is used to remove high frequencies oscillations. In our simulations,

26 we consider $\alpha = 0.6$. The deviatoric stress τ is computed using the Jaumann derivative [1],
27 defined as

$$\left\langle \frac{D\tau_i}{Dt} \right\rangle = \mathbf{\Lambda S}^{-1} \dot{\epsilon}_i + \tau_i \omega_i - \omega_i \tau_i,$$

28 with $\dot{\epsilon}_i = \frac{\langle \nabla u_i \rangle + \langle \nabla u_i \rangle^T}{2}$ and $\omega_i = \frac{\langle \nabla u_i \rangle - \langle \nabla u_i \rangle^T}{2}$.

29 Code

30 Source code for RootSPH model is hosted at the RootSPH repository

31 References

- 32 [1] Ted Belytschko et al. *Nonlinear finite elements for continua and structures*. John Wiley
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- 34 [2] MB Liu and GR Liu. “Smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH): an overview and re-
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- 37 [3] Z.L. Zhang and M.B. Liu. “A decoupled finite particle method for modeling incompress-
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39 633. ISSN: 0307-904X. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2018.03.043>. URL:
40 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0307904X18301677>.

41 **Figure A.** Anisotropy coefficient distribution for case 1.

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43 **Figure B.** Division threshold, softening coefficient, and anisotropy coefficient distributions
44 for case 2 in relation to parameters x , s , and c .

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